

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF SPIRITUAL ETHICAL EDUCATION OF STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF THE HERITAGE OF EASTERN THINKERS

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ANATASIYA: The heritage of our ancestors is the basis for the development of their activities in a specific field with the help of certain talents of the young generation. This creates potential opportunities for the development of the younger generation. The development of cognitive activity in the young generation is directly related to the existing conditions and the content of education. Representation of people's social experience in educational content

KEY WORDS: Teacher, Education, Andragogy, Heritage of ancestors, education, pedagogy, independent reading, didactics, developing society, spirituality, educational process.

Our scientific and practical heritage, created by our ancestors, is unique in the organization of students' in-class, independent work and extracurricular processes. The development of the technology of using a person's heritage related to the development of educational activity in pedagogical practice in the process of teaching the science of "Education" provides the basis for achieving the expected result. For us to realize such visions and expected results

We use such sources as "Theory and History of Pedagogy", "Andragogy" textbooks, "Using hadiths in the formation of the student's spirituality", the monograph "Mechanisms of developing students' educational activities from the heritage of our ancestors". Using these manuals and the heritage of our ancestors, we need to create informational and methodological support, electronic educational resources for students of pedagogical higher education institutions, and on this basis, implement the process of education for students and young people.

By educating the young generation, it acquires spiritual-cultural, intellectual wealth, heritage of ancestors, centuries-old social experience and values of the people. A person interprets the acquired knowledge and social experience as concepts, laws, principles, theories and passes them on to the next generations. The learning process has its own specific stages. Its stages are different depending on the person's level of understanding of the world, forms and methods of cognitive activity. A person's cognitive activity is divided into emotional and intellectual forms of cognition according to its character.

In the process of theoretical knowledge, a person is able to understand the essence of phenomena more deeply. Forms of theoretical knowledge are manifested in accuracy, modeling, abstraction, formalism, theory creation. A person uses certain methods of logical thinking in the process of cognition. They represent a holistic approach to the object being studied, as well as the process of development of things and phenomena. Means of speech and

various signs are of particular importance in the process of human cognition. Because they reflect the indicators of cognitive activity.

Cognitive activity of a person performs certain tasks. With the help of educational tasks, students develop skills to search for new knowledge and information. It creates an opportunity to actively use various concepts and knowledge in the educational process.

In order to solve cognitive tasks, our ancestors put more problematic tasks and questions before the learners. He encouraged them to seek. Through this, they have achieved the development of students' cognitive activities. To do this, they tried to set tasks for students that would encourage them to search, and they achieved the desired result. Completing knowledge tasks requires independence and knowledge from learners. For this purpose, special attention is paid to independent education of students in schools and madrasas. They are more engaged in independent reading. As a result of independent reading, logical observation exercises, students' cognitive activities are developed. As a result, they have satisfaction, positive emotions and motivation to create. That is why in the Middle Ages, most madrasa scholars were engaged in artistic creation.

When approached from a didactic point of view, a person acquires the knowledge necessary for social life in the process of cognitive activity and acquires the skills to apply it in practical activities. This approach has taken priority in the work of Eastern scholars. Especially the madrasa teachers encouraged the students to learn a new subject after they had thoroughly mastered each subject and acquired the necessary practical skills. Cognitive activity is the basis for the birth of various imaginations and ideas. The great scholars who lived in Central Asia paid special attention to the methods of knowledge in order to improve the individual in all aspects. Thinkers such as Abu Rayhan Beruni, Ibn Sina, Abu Nasr Farabi paid special attention to the methods of knowledge in their works. Knowledge methods have a creative nature. Methods of knowledge of allamas divided into empirical and intellectual methods of knowledge. Among the empirical methods of knowledge, experts include observation, experience, description, measurement.

The legacy of our ancestors is the basis for the development of their activities in a specific field with the help of the specific talents of the younger generation. This creates potential opportunities for the development of the younger generation. The development of cognitive activity in the young generation is directly related to the existing conditions and the content of education. Representation of people's social experience in educational content is the basis for the emergence of cognitive activity in the subjects of the process. It ensures that abilities, talent and talent are clearly manifested in them. The heritage of ancestors and pedagogical conditions play an important role in the formation of cognitive abilities of young people. These didactic tools help to develop anatomical and morphological abilities of students.

We need to have the skills to effectively use the heritage of our ancestors in order to supply well-rounded specialists to today's developing society.

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